

Management of Solid Urban Waste and the Participation of its Actors

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Abstract

Solid waste comes from the inorganic and organic waste that is generated during the activities of daily life of people and companies. Which if not properly managed generate pollution and risks to public health (Ariza-Díaz, Andrea and Sánchez-De La Torre, Valeria1, 2020), for these reasons it is an obligatory issue in national, regional and local public policies in different countries of the world, which are regulated by laws to oblige and guarantee compliance, Added to this is the importance of the active involvement of its actors (public and private sectors and the population as a whole); this joint work must be framed in the solid waste management of the commune, based on treatment models (Dos Santos, Crislaine Aparecida Pereira and de Souza, Janaína Dos Santos, 2016).

INTRODUCTION

Solid waste comes from the inorganic and organic waste that is generated during the activities of daily life of people and companies. Which if not properly managed generate pollution and risks to public health (Ariza-Díaz, Andrea and Sánchez-De La Torre, Valeria1, 2020), for these reasons it is an obligatory issue in national, regional and local public policies in different countries of the world, which are regulated by laws to oblige and guarantee compliance, Added to this is the importance of the active involvement of its actors (public and private sectors and the population as a whole); this joint work must be framed in the solid waste management of the commune, based on treatment models (Dos Santos, Crislaine Aparecida Pereira and de Souza, Janaína Dos Santos, 2016).

Having inadequate solid waste management will have a negative effect on the environment and the health of the population in general, with cities losing their ability to receive when the environment becomes dirty due to the garbage that has been disposed of outdoors, since such a condition leads to the proliferation of insects

and rodents, as well as dirt and odors resulting from the decomposition process; Not to mention the state of the landscape, which with garbage deteriorates and has a negative impact on mental health due to the feelings of restlessness and discomfort that is generated by the presence of solid waste.

It is specified that the Local Municipalities are the ones that have the responsibility to generate awareness and guide the population for its proper management (Law of integral management of solid waste Peru, D.L.N°1278) using methodologies and perspectives of citizen science to deal with the issue (Albagli, S, and Rocha, L, 2020), having to implement different strategies with the aim of involving and generating active participation of each member of the community, improving their skills in the treatment of their solid waste, motivating reflection on the conservation of the environment, minimizing public health risks (Maiello, A. and Britto, ALNP, 2018) and shortening the existing gaps between the actions carried out by the local government and the actions of its population with the management and management of solid waste.

In this last part, it highlights that the economic and educational issue on the part of the population and the inadequate management of the local government (Ariza-Díaz and Sánchez-De La Torre, 2020) are the limitations to shorten this gap, having to focus on the formalization of solid waste recycling and reformulating its environmental and social policies (Bonelli, JM, 2018), based on sustainable management that coincide in the active participation of all actors, framed in efficient management by local authorities (Saputra and Saat 2019); it is necessary to evaluate the performance of waste management results through the use of sustainability indicators (Barros RTV and Silveira A., 2019).

It should be noted that an important aspect in the active participation of the population (Ariza-Díaz, Andrea and Sánchez-De La Torre, 2020) is transparency in the management of local authorities (Rodríguez Martín and Palomo Zurdo, 2020), as well as the realization of an integrated solid waste management plan (Chaves, GLD and Siman RR, 2020). It is therefore important that the government of the day plans and implements a management plan for solid waste in its commune, which should be transparent to the general public and other stakeholders.

For the above, the objective of this work is to identify, examine, systematically the best available scientific evidence on solid waste management in municipalities analyzing the participation of its actors, available in the SCOPUS and EBSCO database free of charge of the last five years; having as hypothesis that, the largest volume of scientific evidence available on the management of solid waste in municipalities focuses significantly on management and treatment and not on the participation of its actors.

DEVELOPMENT

This work begins with the entry into the bases of SCOPUS and EBSCO, carrying out the search for the terms "solid waste", "Municipal management", "quality of management", "social responsibility" and "environmental responsibility", discarding articles that are not linked to the search topics and whose publications are not generated before 2015; obtaining for analysis, 25 documents with relevance to the topic (22 in Spanish and 3 in English) from a total of 401 works found, highlighting that 88% of the final search results belong to SCOPUS. The methodology used in the design and writing of this article highlights the mixed method (scientific method, synthetic analytical method), the design of non-experimental research and an explanatory descriptive research level.

For the literature review, the following were considered:

1) Planning, the search details were specified (protocol) and with this the collection of articles was carried out systematically; The following steps have been taken:

- Elaboration of the search chain:

"solid waste" OR "Municipal management" OR "quality of management" AND "social responsibility" OR "environmental responsibility")

- Identification of information sources:

SCOPUS and EBSCO bibliographic database

- All search fields were chosen (All fields option) in the two databases (title, keyword, etc.).

- Definition of inclusion criteria

It was classified in the criteria:

a) Linguistic criteria, articles and communications were collected in English and Spanish).

b) Time criterion, articles of 2015 and 2021 were considered.

c) Thematic criterion, its area of application and related sciences are established.

d) Exclusion criterion, repetitive results were eliminated, discarding articles that are not related to the topic.

2) Execution of the search protocol, "results" were obtained that were interpreted and analyzed.

Using the search string in SCOPUS and EBSCO, 401 publications were obtained between 2015 and 2021. With these preliminary results, the thematic and relevant linguistic criterion was applied with a sample of 25 documents (22 in Spanish and 3 in English), which includes both variables (X and Y) and as detailed in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Search protocol phases

Source: Authors.

3) Results, this part presents the results of the 25 articles that were the subject of study and analysis, fulfilling all the inclusion criteria applied, showing a summary of the articles in Table I, II, III.

Table I Resulting Publications After the Systematic Search.

No.	Title	Authorship	Country	Publication Date	Code
1	Multicriteria analysis of alternatives For the treatment of solid municipal waste in the municipality of Juazeiro do north ceará	Müller LNPES, Arruda JBF, Alcantara RLC y Pereira RL	Brazil	2021	A1
2	Overview of the disposal of municipal solid waste and its relationship with the social environmental impacts in states of the Brazilian Amazon	From Aguiar E.S, Viana J.H. y Pontes, A.N	Brazil	2021	A2
3	MSW management: a review of key elements of an environmental problem and persistent debate	Latasa I. Lozano PJ and Bueno, G.	Spain	2021	A3
4	Actors, epistemic communities and political change: analysis of solid waste policy in Guarulhos	Da Silva Leite, C.K. y De Lócco, L.G.	Brazil	2020	A4
5	An analysis of intermunicipal consortia for solid waste treatment services based on institutional collective action	Fernandes, A.S.A., Pinheiro, L.S.ascimento, A.B.F.M. y, Grin, E.J.d	Brazil	2020	A5
6	Assessment tool for municipal integrated solid waste management plans: Part 2	Chaves GLD, Siman RR y Sena LG	Brazil	2020	A6
7	Citizen science on the subject of solid waste	Albagli S y Rocha, L.	Brazil	2020	A7
8	Management of municipal waste and institutional environment in Rio Grande do Sul	Carbonai, D. a , Baum, J. b , Camiz, S.	Brazil	2020	A8
9	Solid Waste: Poor Public Management as an Environmental Problem	Luz Bezerra, A, Franco Rocha y Moita Neto, JM	Brazil	2020	A9
10	Municipal solid waste management in Latin America: An analysis from the perspective of generation	Sánchez-Muñoz, M.D.P, Cruz-Cerón, J.G. and Maldonado-Espinel	Colombia	2020	A10
11	Multicriteria model for the integral management of municipal solid waste in Quevedo, Ecuador	Quinteros PA, González JK, Delgado FM and Casanova, BM	Ecuador	2020	A11
12	Transparency and circular economy: analysis and valuation of municipal solid waste management	Rodríguez Martín, Palomo-Zurdo, and González-Sánchez, F.	Spain	2020	A12

No.	Title	Authorship	Country	Publication Date	Code
13	Community diagnosis for integrated solid waste management. Case study: Barrio Fredonia, Cartagena.	Ariza-Díaz, Andrea1 Sánchez-De La Torre, Valeria Bahamón-Restrepo, Andrés and Díaz-Mendoza,	Colombia	2020	A13
14	A study on sustainable solid waste management on Perhentian Island, Malaysia	Saat, SA y Saputra, J.	Malaysia	2019	A14
15	Characterization of household solid waste management in the city of Villavicencio	Polanco, HR and Garcia, DF	Colombia	2019	A15
16	Use of sustainability indicators for the evaluation of municipal solid waste management in the metropolitan region of Belo Horizonte, MG, Brazil	Barros, RTV , Silveira, A.VF	Brazil	2019	A16
17	Environmental protection, labor and social inclusion: formalizing the recycling of municipal solid waste in Buenos Aires	Bonelli, JM	Argentina	2018	A17
18	Implementation of the Brazilian national policy for waste management	Maiello, A. Britto, ALNP and Valle, TF c	Brazil	2018	A18
19	Economic valuation in the selective collection of solid waste	Feitosa AK, Barden JE, Konrad O y Matos, MAA	Brazil	2018	A19
20	Use of indicators in solid urban waste administration: A methodological construction proposal and analysis by cities and regions: Request for The model	Pereira, SS	Brazil	2018	A20
21	Analysis of urban solid waste management in the municipalities of the state of Rio de Janeiro and the role of landfills in reducing environmental impacts	Contrera, JMAD , Almeida, FS y Santos, CA Andrade	Brazil	2018	A21
22	Setbacks municipal administrative capacity and national solid waste policy	Chaves, GLD, Santos Junior, JL and Rocha, SMS	Brazil	2017	A22
23	Sustainability and municipal solid waste. Comparative analysis of the different treatment models for Guipúzcoa (Basque Autonomous Community)	Valencia PJL, Zaballos IL and Mendieta GB	Spain	2017	A23

No.	Title	Authorship	Country	Publication Date	Code
24	The role of public policies in the conservation of natural waste	dos Santos, Crislaine Aparecida Pereira, de Souza, Janaína dos Santos, de Souza, Ana Lúcia Almeida ydos Santos, Valdemara Cristiane Pereira	Brazil	2016	A24
25	Diagnosis of urban solid waste management in the municipality of Mexicali, Mexico: Challenges for achieving sustainable planning	Calva Alejo, C.L. Email Author and Rojas Caldelas, R.I.	Mexico	2015	A25

Source: Authors.

Table II Results and conclusions of the resulting publications after the systematic search.

Code	Results	Conclusions
A1	The results presented took into account a set of premises of ideal scenarios (recycling, separation and sale, landfill, biomanagers, incineration and sale of the energy generated.	The techniques of treatment of municipal solid waste provide us with management alternatives on the subject.
A2	Even with the active exploitation of its natural resources and economic potential, the Amazon region lags behind in terms of life expectancy, educational attainment and income, suggesting that exploitation is not providing the local population with the benefits of high quality of life. In addition, there are cultural problems with the population and the solid waste they produce.	The proper final disposal of solid waste is a challenge that the Amazon must prioritize because it already represents a risk of contamination. Government incentives are required to reduce adverse socio-environmental effects.
A3	Economic considerations aside, it is impossible to recycle all materials since, according to the second law of thermodynamics, doing so results in a progressive degradation of the original materials.	It is possible to develop scientifically sound arguments to support each of the current beliefs about possible solid waste management models.
A4	There is disagreement about the public policy tools available for solid waste disposal.	The entry of new actors, experts from the solid waste research community, disrupted the local monopoly created through the use of political power.
A5	Analysis of the results of the restructuring of political network structures revealed that participation in cooperation is more likely for aldermen who are not members of the governor's political group.	This study used an interdisciplinary approach to examine the factors that Brazilian local governments consider when deciding whether to join inter-municipal coalitions that provide solid waste disposal services.
A6	The results show that the proposed tool is consistent and identifies points for improvement in solid waste management.	The proposal of the tool for solid waste management is integrated, as well as its procedure guide.

Code	Results	Conclusions
A7	There is a higher incidence of plastic waste generated by the population	Contextualize the issue of solid waste on a global level
A8	Problems and solutions are defined, reformulated and reviewed at various points in the public policy and decision-making cycle, and current decisions are considered dependent on previous ones.	Best practices in waste management depend on repeated local government management policies and practices.
A9	The results showed the difficulty in implementing procedures by municipal administrators and the need to review current laws regarding solid waste.	Public waste has become an environmental problem and requires public administration and national policies.
A10	Looking at the overall results, it is surprising to find that there is no clear correlation between environmental performance and the city's income level, which was calculated as the average GDP per person for this study.	The study of urban waste generation aims to contribute to the achievement of sustainable development. The importance of raising awareness among citizens about their role in reducing solid waste is highlighted.
A11	The model gives us savings due to the environmental impact	The main problems can be identified by analysing the current situation of the municipal solid waste chain.
A12	Transparency in management is 42.6%	Highlights the low level of transparency with solid waste management
A13	Most of the population does not know the proper management they should give to solid waste	Strategies are identified to treat and solve the problem of solid waste
A14	People don't know how to store garbage, suggesting improvement in service	The public and private sectors have an important role to play in managing the solid waste problem.
A15	The main problem is citizen culture and social indiscipline	Low communication between actors, the policies given by municipalities are weak on the issue
A16	Deficiency in waste management	There is precariousness of public services with the attention of solid waste, the use of indicators is a tool for decision-making
A17	The integrated waste management approach is a more environmentally and socially responsible model than the conventional one.	The inclusion of the socio-labour forces of waste pickers makes the integrated waste management approach more environmentally friendly.
A18	The data collected and processed reflect the low recycling capacity of the governments of the day	The development of an urban solid waste management framework is crucial for municipalities, as the research reveals a weak commitment on their part to management.
A19	91.94% of respondents recognize that the collection contributes to the reduction of pollution, but only 37.50% would be willing to pay for the referred collection	Gender, income and education factors were associated with a greater or lesser willingness to pay. the services in question.

Code	Results	Conclusions
A20	No municipality analyzed, promotes solid waste management or uses indicators smaller municipalities have greater management problems.	The seven municipalities surveyed have serious deficiencies in the execution of services related to solid waste management in all dimensions investigated
A21	More than 60% of municipalities do not follow household urban waste disposal standards, and the percentage of this waste that is recycled in most municipalities is quite low. Decrease in the number of landfills.	The decrease in the number of dumps is probably due to each municipality's attempt to fit into the National Solid Waste Policy. However, most of them still failed to adapt the legislation.
A22	Absence of local administrative capacity	Unplanned urban and economic growth has a direct impact on increasing solid waste production, which requires effective public policies on environmental sanitation.
A23	The result is that a scenario of management and treatment of urban waste for the study territory that avoids using incineration as a preferable objective, the treatment option seems quite feasible thus producing a balance of the economic, material and energy.	As a result of the significant decrease in the amount of raw materials consumed by the world, various instruments are being used to boost a circular economy, as well as the promotion of prevention as well as the promotion of recycling and reuse.
A24	The public policy currently in force is the conservation and proper use of natural resources through environmental education.	The different legal frameworks reveal an evolution in the legal apparatus for the protection of the environment and quality of life. However, legislation alone has not been sufficient to address environmental problems.
A25	The transition from rural to urban areas altered society's consumption patterns from one that produced primarily organic waste to one that produced primarily inorganic waste derived from consumption patterns typical of urban industrial societies.	Sustainable urban solid waste planning requires a long-term vision, which the municipality now lacks due to its transitional administrations, which are mostly based on rapid response tactics, but which would require a long-term strategic plan.

Source: Authors.

Table III Contributions of the Resulting Publications After the Systematic Search.

Code	Contribution
A1	Alternatives for the treatment of solid waste
A2	Socio-environmental impacts - Solid waste,
A3	Elements of solid waste, key to an environmental problem and a persistent debate.
A4	Solid waste policy (Actors, epistemic communities and political change)
A5	Solid waste treatment services based on institutional collective action
A6	Assessment tool, integrated solid waste management
A7	Citizen science on the subject of solid waste
A8	Municipal management (Solid waste)
A9	Public Administration, solid waste management as an environmental problem

Code	Contribution
A10	Analysis of Municipal Solid Waste Management in Latin America
A11	Multicriteria model for the integral management of municipal solid waste
A12	Transparency and circular economy: analysis and valuation of municipal solid waste management
A13	Community diagnosis for integrated solid waste management
A14	Sustainable solid waste management
A15	Characterization of household solid waste management
A16	Sustainability indicators for the evaluation of municipal solid waste management
A17	Environmental protection, labour and social inclusion - Municipal solid waste
A18	Implementation of policies for waste management
A19	Economic valuation in the selective collection of solid waste
A20	Use of indicators - solid residues
A21	Analysis of solid waste management and the role of landfills in reducing environmental impacts
A22	Municipal administrative capacity and solid waste policies
A23	Sustainability and municipal solid waste.
A24	Public policies in the conservation of natural waste
A25	Diagnosis of municipal solid waste management - Challenges for achieving sustainable planning

Source: Authors.

Regarding the methodology, eight (08) of the articles studied have used qualitative methods equivalent to 32% of the final search results, three (03) have used quantitative methods equivalent to 12% of the final search results and fourteen (14) mixed methods equivalent to 56% of the final search results. The detail can be seen in Figure 2 and Table IV detailed below.

Figure 2 Methodology Used by the Reviewed Articles

Table IV Contributions of the Resulting Publications After the Systematic Search

CODE	METHODOLOGIES		
	Qualitative	Quantitative	Mixed
A1			X
A2			X
A3			X
A4	X		
A5	X		
A6			X
A7			X
A8			X
A9			X
A10			X
A11		x	
A12	X		
A13			x
A14	x		
A15			x
A16		X	
A17	x		

CODE	METHODOLOGIES		
	Qualitative	Quantitative	Mixed
A18			x
A19		x	
A20			X
A21			x
A22	x		
A23			x
A24	x		
A25	x		

Source: Authors.

Among the 25 articles that are the result of the filter carried out, it stands out in figures 3, 4 and 5 that 88% come from the SCOPUS bibliographic database (22 articles) and 12% from EBSCO (3 articles); maintaining the scientific production filtered in the analyzed databases, a growth of production. It is specified that the filter cut made is to May 2021.

Figure 3 and 4 Number of Articles % of Article

Figure 5 Publications by Year

Source: Authors.

According to figures 6 and 7, the evaluation of the scientific production filtered in the analyzed databases shows that the country with the most treatment on the subject is Brazil with a 60% share, followed by Colombia and Spain with 12% participation respectively. Among the authors from Brazil, the works of Müller, Arruda Alcantara and Pereira (2021), De Aguiar, Viana and Pontes (2021), of Spain Latasa, Lozano and Bueno (2021) and of Colombia Sánchez-Muñoz, Cruz-Cerón, and Maldonado (2020) stand out.

Figure 6 Publications by Country

Authors.

Figure 7 Percentage of Publications by Country

Source: Authors.

CONCLUSIONS

Summary and analysis

Within the results of the systematic review, the similarities of the topics predominate: solid waste, management and treatment with 44% participation and on the other hand and with less amount the environmental impact with 4% and models and tools with 20% participation; clearly highlights that the largest volume of scientific evidence available on solid waste management in municipalities focuses significantly on management and treatment and not on the participation of its actors, proving the hypothesis initially proposed.

The above detail is described in Tables V and VI as well as in Figure 8.

Table V and Figure 8 Similarities – Quantity Similarities – Quantity %

Similarities	Quantity
Solid waste - Management - Treatment	44%
Actors - Policies	32%
Model and Tools	20%
Environmental impact	4%
Total, general	100%

Source: Authors.

Table VI Predominant similarities

SAMPLE	CODE	Total
Solid Residuos - Management - Treatment	A1	4%
	A10	4%
	A15	4%
	A19	4%
	A2	4%
	A21	4%
	A23	4%
	A25	4%
	A3	4%
A5	4%	
A8	4%	
Total, Solid waste - Management - Treatment		44%
Actors - policies	A12	4%
	A14	4%
	A18	4%
	A22	4%
	A24	4%
	A4	4%
	A7	4%
	A9	4%
Total, ACTORS - POLICIES		32%
Model and tool	A11	4%
	A13	4%
	A16	4%
	A20	4%
A6	4%	
Total, Model and Tool		20%
Environmental impact	A17	4%
Total, environmental impact		4%
Total, general		100%

On the other hand, solid waste is directly related to the problem of the environment affecting the population and its environment, especially in public health, environmental factors (renewable and non-renewable resources), social factors (public health) and economic factors (natural resources), for this public administrators must plan and implement alternatives for solid waste management (Müller and Arruda, 2021). However, the selection of waste and its treatment is a complex process that must consider different criteria such as economic, environmental, social, technical and regulatory; likewise (De Aguiar E.S, Viana J.H, 2021) highlights the reuse of waste, thus significantly reducing the need for landfills, considering garbage as a primary component in other industries that can add value to the waste of others (D.L. N°1278 – Ministry of Environment Peru). Retrieved from <https://www.minam.gob.pe/>. Therefore, public health is seriously affected by the problem of environmental pollution, a fact that must be addressed by the authorities of the day through policies and active participation of the actors, taking advantage of the generation of resources through the reuse of waste.

It should be mentioned, in addition and according to (Latasa and Lozano, 2021) that there are still governments that have debates on the administration of Municipal Solid Waste, there are disagreements and confrontations at the political and public level that prevent implementation and action on the subject, highlighting that bibliometric and thematic analysis evidences the growing interest of the research community around the subject and the existence of often contradictory visions that divide experts and that show the need to reorient the existing debate. The adoption of citizen science methodologies and approaches to address the issue of solid waste, according to (Albagli S and Rocha, 2020) provide a

panorama that contextualizes the theme of the topic. Therefore, not having agreements between the actors on the administration of solid waste is a serious limitation on the actions to be taken on the subject, even more so if the population does not carry out scientific work guided by specialists actions that must be motivated by the governments of the day.

The mismanagement of municipal solid waste negatively impacts the environment and directly on the health of the population. Cities and population centers decrease their welcoming capacity when their environment becomes unhealthy this by the generation of disposed garbage that is outdoors, since such a scenario begins the proliferation of rodents and insects, as well as the generation of bad odors that come from the process of decomposition, to this is added the tarnishing of the landscape, which impacts on mental health due to the perception of insecurity and discomfort (MINAM) Recovered from <https://www.minam.gob.pe/>. Therefore, if you want to have an environment where the good health of the population prevails, as well as its life expectancy, it is important that solid waste management aims to mitigate and reduce the negative impact generated by poor waste management.

On the other hand, efficiency in what concerns the management of solid waste does not depend only on the municipalities that are responsible for the administration, but also on their population since their habits and customs have an important role with the subject, this being a variable in which it must be actively worked by the municipal authorities. No public cleaning system will be able to operate optimally if the population it serves does not have adequate environmental education, which is reflected through their habits and customs (MINAM) Recovered from <https://www.minam.gob.pe/>

On the other hand (da Silva Leite, and De Lócco, 2020), he affirms that to address the issue of urban solid waste there must be a political change where the actors of the population and their authorities participate using public policy instruments promoting its industrialization (D.L. N°1278 – Ministry of Environment Peru) <https://www.minam.gob.pe/> Likewise (Chaves and Siman, 2020) highlights the importance of the gestation of a Municipal Plan for Integrated Solid Waste Management using tools for its evaluation, which must have four complementary indices that are: Service Index, Quality Index, Complexity Index and Potential Index. In addition (Barros and Silveira, 2019) highlights that the performance of public policies for solid waste management should be evaluated through the use of sustainability indicators, in the same way (Pereira, 2018) emphasizes the use of indicators in the management of urban solid waste, with its analysis it is possible to focus specific actions to address the issue. Therefore, if there are no policies that address the problem in detail or if sustainability indicators are not used that serve as a framework for integrated management, adequate management of solid waste will not be carried out since specific actions will not be focused to address the issue.

Likewise, the economic valuation of solid waste collection and the identification of its variables (Feitosa and Barden, 2018) play an important role within municipal management since the greater or lesser willingness of the population to pay for the referred services are often related to the gender variables, income and education. It is also important that the sustainability (Saat and Saputra, 2019) of solid waste management (Valencia and Zaballos, 2017) is maintained over time and within a long-term work plan, guided by standards, stimuli, proposals, technological solutions,

technical support and training at the decentralized level, education and citizenship programs (Ministry of Environment – Peru) Recovered from <https://www.minam.gob.pe/> . It must be evaluated periodically and depending on the results, refine the strategies to be implemented to achieve the objectives set in the administration of urban solid waste by governments and their population, seeing solid waste as resources and not as possible threats (D.L. N°1278 – Ministry of Environment Peru) Retrieved from <https://www.minam.gob.pe/>. Consequently, it is important to motivate the participation of the population both in the economic aspect and in the active participation within the solid waste management of the community, facts that must be evaluated periodically to execute the necessary and/or corrective measures to achieve the objectives set by the governments of the day regarding the subject.

It should be mentioned that fifteen years after the issuance of the General Law of Solid Waste in Peru, there are still problems of public cleanliness. The unplanned growth of cities has a direct impact on the increase in solid waste emissions (Chaves, and Santos, 2017). In addition, every day there are more urban and rural inhabitants, therefore, there is more generation of garbage and that on average a Peruvian generates more than half a kilo a day, (MINAM) Recovered from <https://www.minam.gob.pe/>.

On the other hand, the Regional Governments are dynamic actors in the administration of solid waste (MINAM) Recovered from <https://www.minam.gob.pe/> since they must develop and implement public, private or mixed investment programs for the implementation of solid waste infrastructures within the framework of their jurisdiction, always in conjunction with the municipalities

of the area, approving projects and their environmental management instruments (Art. 21 D.L. N°1278), for their part, the Provincial Municipalities have the competence to plan and approve all integral management in the geographical area of their competence, regulating and supervising the management of solid waste, promoting and guiding agreements between the district municipalities with the objective of generating economies of scale framed in the efficiency of waste management always generating lower social and environmental impacts (Art. 22 D.L. No. 1278); on the other hand, the district municipalities are responsible for the administration of solid waste of domestic origin, special and similar, within the scope of their power, ensuring an adequate cleaning, collection and transport service of solid waste, guaranteeing an adequate disposal of waste (Art. 24 D.L. N°1278), always with the active participation of the population (da Silva Leite, and De Lócco, 2020). The Municipalities must have technical capacity (planning, operation, supervision of services), capacity in their internal organization (with strengthened and trained teams), commercial organization (charging the citizen with a fair price for the service they provide) and their ability to instruct the neighbor and sensitize him so that he does NOT dirty the community and pays in a timely manner his taxes (MINAM) Recovered from <https://www.minam.gob.pe/> . In the same way, the population for its part has a fundamental role that begins with putting the garbage in the right place in a timely manner, as well as the payment of taxes. The public cleaning service has a cost for society (MINAM) recovered from <https://www.minam.gob.pe/> and is not free, and must be assumed by the citizens who are beneficiaries of said service. Therefore, the active participation of the actors is crucial

within the management of solid waste since if one of them is not aligned with the objectives, the best results in terms of the management of this waste will not be achieved.

It is also important that all solid waste management must comply with the process of cleaning public places, segregation, storage, collection, recovery, transport, transfer and treatment, as well as the final disposal (Art. 31 Legislative Decree No. 1278 - Peru) and its valuation is based on the waste being reused, focused on serving in a useful way replacing other resources within the productive chain, being its energy recovery or material ((Art. 31 Legislative Decree No. 1278 - Peru)). In addition, it is necessary to have an infrastructure for the management of solid waste and this must be composed of solid waste collection centers, a recovery and transfer plant, as well as a material final disposal structure (Art. 31 Legislative Decree No. 1278 - Peru). Therefore, it is necessary to establish in a timely manner what to do and how to do solid waste management, considering the infrastructure and the costs that this entails, all aligned with a work plan provided by the authorities on duty.

It should be noted that the review and analysis carried out in this work allowed us to identify examples of management from different perspectives on solid waste management where its actors play an important role on the subject, covering from the diagnosis of solid waste management (Calva-Alejo and Rojas-Caldelas, 2015) its analysis (Contrera and Almeida, 2018), review of its key elements (Latasa and Lozano, 2021), Implementation of waste management policies (Maiello and Britto, 2018), Use of sustainability indicators (Barros and Silveira, 2019), its economic valuation (Feitosa and Barden, 2018) (Rodriguez and Palomo, 2020), always seeking citizen

participation minimizing public health risks (Maiello and Britto, 2018), framed in environmental protection and social inclusion (Bonelli, 2018).

Tendency

Only 20% of the articles reviewed and analyzed present a model to be used in the treatment and management of municipal solid waste, considering and proposing tools for its management; On the other hand, only 4% of the articles reviewed and analyzed highlight the environmental impact generated by poor solid waste management hand in hand with a low participation of the actors, all this gives us a wide horizon for new studies and / or proposals for improvement.

It highlights that poor management in the management of solid waste and absence of the participation of the actors, puts the health of the population at direct risk.

Proposal

It is essential that the Municipalities carry out an initial assessment of the situation in which the management of solid waste is so that from it the strategies and objectives to be achieved in the short, medium and long term are planned, all hand in hand and with the participation of the population, to this end, it is necessary for municipalities to strengthen the capacity to educate and sensitize their population.

In order to achieve the best solid waste management by the Municipalities, it is necessary to develop a solid waste management plan, which is a management instrument that is born from a coordinated and agreed development between authorities and municipal officials, as well as representatives of local, public and private institutions, promoting an ideal management and administration of solid waste, ensuring

sustainability framed in efficiency and effectiveness, from its generation to its final disposal, considering minimization processes: reduction, reuse and recycling of solid waste where recyclers who are formalized are included and for this it is suggested that this plan entails 04 stages that are: (Ministry of Environment Peru). Retrieved from <https://www.minam.gob.pe/>

1. Organization and Planning, where the Municipality will form a technical team with people with the necessary knowledge and / or experience in the subject; Those who will carry out the work plan must also identify and coordinate with local actors, developing participatory workshops that consist of the elaboration of the tree of problems which will allow objectivity and consensus.

2. Diagnosis, analyze the physical environment and the institutional situation, as well as the operational technical aspects developing a matrix of gaps and needs, this to have the information to formulate actions that contribute to a better integral management, as well as an adequate management of solid waste.

3. Formulation, establish the means and objectives identifying alternative solutions by developing the action plan to be developed in a period of 05 years, considering short, medium and long-term measures through goals that can be executed according to the reality of the district.

4. Follow-up and monitoring, establishing the responsible unit, as well as the preparation of the matrix of activities and the sending of progress reports, all in order to know at all times the problems that may arise in order to solve them immediately.

The aforementioned stages focus on carrying out an orderly, technical and participatory process among all actors.

It should be noted that the solid waste that must be considered in the aforementioned Plan are household, market, commercial, educational institutions, weeds and street sweeping (MINAM) Recovered from <https://www.minam.gob.pe/>

On the other hand, at present, the recycling of solid waste is an economic opportunity that can favor both municipalities and the population, in the case of the latter to generate companies linked to the subject; in this sense, recycling allows recovering, transforming and elaborating materials from waste (Castells, 2012), responding to various activities that are carried out based on the different states of waste that can be used and thereby reducing the volume of solid waste in landfills reducing pollution and health problems (Sullivan Sealey & Smith, 2014).

It should also be noted that the purpose of solid waste management is to prevent and minimize the generation of these, recovering and valuing them, finding in them reuse, recycling, among other alternatives based on the guarantee of the protection of health and environment (Art. 2 Legislative Decree No. 1278 - Peru).

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